

Original article

Pattern Of Morbidity and Mortality at the Emergency Paediatric Unit of a Tertiary Hospital in North-Eastern Nigeria

Maimuna O Yusuf,^{1,2} Dalhat S Afegbua,^{1,2} Peter A Shaibu,² Ibrahim Yahaya,² Ibrahim Gideon,² Rilwanu Yahaya,² Bello A. Ibrahim,^{1,2} Iragbogie A. Imoudu,^{1,2} Ismaik K Musa,² Lamidi I Audu.^{1,2}

¹Department of Paediatrics, Faculty of Clinical Sciences, Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare, Bauchi State.

²Department of Paediatrics, Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare

Corresponding Author: Maimuna O. YUSUF Email: memzii@yahoo.com Tel: 234-8036342501

Abstract

Background: Since 1990, there has been a global decline in infant and child mortality rates attributed to various public health interventions. However, developing countries, especially those in Sub-Saharan Africa and South-East Asia, have the worst indices of childhood mortality. **Objective:** This study aims to describe the causes of mortality, morbidity, and the outcomes of care provided to children seen in the emergency paediatric unit of the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare. **Materials and Methods:** This was a retrospective, cross-sectional study. All children aged 1 month to 15 years seen at the emergency paediatric unit of our hospital from January 1 to December 31, 2024, were recruited. Data was analysed with IBM SPSS version 21 software. **Results:** A total of 2973 children were studied in the year under review, with an age range of 1 month to 15 years. The median (Interquartile range) age was 3.0 (6.5) years, with most children (60.6%) aged less than 5 years and a male predominance of 1720 (57.9%). The common causes of morbidity were severe malaria 871(29.3%), malnutrition 414(13.9%) and sickle cell disease 347 (11.7%) while severe malaria 93(30.0%), malnutrition 62(20.0%) and pneumonia 27(8.7%) were the commonest causes of mortality. The unit had an overall mortality rate of 10.4%. The majority of admissions occurred during the rainy season 1293(43.5%). **Conclusion:** Infections, especially malaria, remain a significant cause of morbidity and mortality amongst children in our study. Uptake of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprophylaxis and childhood vaccinations, as well as other preventive measures, should be encouraged.

Keywords: Emergency Paediatrics Unit, Morbidity, Mortality, Outcome

Open Access article distribution in the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC by 4.0)

Copyright: The Author(s). 2025

ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865

<https://doi.org/>

Date Submitted 10th May, 2025

Date Accepted 18th June 2025

Date Published 30th June, 2025

Cited this article as: Maimuna O Yusuf, Dalhat S Afegbua, Peter A Shaibu, Ibrahim Yahaya, Ibrahim Gideon, Rilwanu Yahaya, Bello A. Ibrahim, Iragbogie A. Imoudu, Ismaik K Musa, Lamidi I Audu. Pattern Of Morbidity and Mortality at the Emergency Paediatric Unit of A Tertiary Hospital in North-Eastern Nigeria *The Scholar J Health Scie* 2025; 1 (1): 64-71

Introduction

Childhood morbidity and mortality remain significant public health challenges, particularly in

emergency paediatric settings where timely and effective interventions are critical. There is a paucity of adequate equipment and staffing to deliver these essential interventions in resource-constrained settings. The emergency paediatric unit serves as a frontline for managing acute and life-threatening conditions in children, whose deaths are often traumatic to their families and the management team.¹ Child morbidity and hospital admissions are also considered financial burdens to the government, health systems and parents.² There has been a worldwide decrease in infant and child mortality rates since 1990, following various public health interventions.³ However, developing countries, especially Sub-Saharan Africa and South-East Asia, have the worst indices of childhood mortality, with both regions constituting more than 80 % of the global 4.9 million under-five deaths in 2022.⁴ In Nigeria, infant and under-five mortality rates, which contribute a significant proportion to deaths in children, have both declined gradually over the past 25 years. Yet, these indices have

remained steady at 74 and 117 deaths per 1,000 live births, respectively, over the past 5 years.⁵ In Africa, preventable and treatable conditions such as pneumonia, diarrhoeal diseases, malnutrition, neonatal diseases and malaria continue to significantly contribute to childhood morbidity and deaths, especially in low- and middle-income countries.^{3,6}

Despite advances in paediatric healthcare, emergency units in tertiary hospitals still face high rates of morbidity and mortality due to late presentation, limited resources and varying disease burdens. Several studies describing morbidity and mortality patterns and outcomes in children admitted into the emergency wards, within and outside Nigeria, have been published.⁷⁻²¹

A similar study conducted in this facility in 2015 by Yauba et al. showed that severe malaria, severe acute malnutrition, and pneumonia were significant causes of mortality in the emergency unit.²¹

A review of the pattern of morbidity and mortality in our emergency paediatric unit would accord us the opportunity to assess the progress made in the last ten years as well as the efficiency of our health system towards achieving Sustainable Development Goal 3 target 2, which is to end preventable deaths of newborns and children under the age of 5 by 2030.²⁴

By identifying the most common diagnoses at admission, age-specific diagnoses, seasonal variations, causes of mortality and outcomes, this study would provide evidence-based insights to improve emergency paediatric care, assist healthcare providers to recognise high-risk conditions and prioritise urgent interventions. It would also enhance decision in resource allocation, critical staff recruitment as well as development of impactful prevention and treatment protocols. Findings from this study will also ultimately enhance local and national data on the causes of morbidity and mortality in children.

Materials and Methods

Study area and site

The study was conducted at the Emergency Paediatric Unit (EPU) of the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, a tertiary healthcare centre serving adults and children in Azare and nearby towns in Bauchi, Jigawa, and Yobe States. The region experiences a rainy season from late May to late September, and the dry season runs from late September to late April. The warmer months are usually from March to May.²² The hottest month is April, while the coldest month is

December.²² The town has nine primary healthcare centres, one secondary and one tertiary healthcare facility with several private clinics serving it and its environs.

The EPU of FUHSTHA is a 30-bed ward where all children aged 1 month to 15 years with emergent medical conditions are managed. The unit is staffed by nurses, medical officers, a Senior registrar, and a consultant daily, on a weekly rotation, as well as other supportive staff on a 24-hour basis. Children sent into this unit are triaged, clinically evaluated, resuscitated, stabilised for 24 to 72 hours and transferred out for full recovery to the Paediatric Medical Ward or to the Paediatric Surgical Ward as required. Children may also be referred to other tertiary facilities for specialised care and intervention if these services are unavailable at our facility. Fully recovered children may also be discharged directly from the unit to be followed up at the Paediatric outpatient unit. This unit had an average of two thousand five hundred and seventy-two (2572) annual admissions in the last 5 years, as derived from the admission register.

Study design/population

The study was a retrospective, hospital-based study involving all children aged 1 month to 15 years (as of their last birthday), seen in the emergency paediatric unit of the FUHSTHA, from January 1, 2024, to December 31, 2024, with complete medical records. Participants were recruited based on the admission register. Patients brought in dead were excluded.

Data collection and management

A semi-structured form designed in the department was used to collect information from the unit. It contained information on the age, gender, address, clinical diagnosis, date of admission, date of discharge and the outcome of treatment. Three research assistants were assigned to collect and summarise the above information. Data collected was checked for correct filling and completeness by the lead researcher. Age was grouped as follows: Infants (< 1 year of age), Under 5 (from 1 year to < 5 years of age), and older child (\geq 5 years of age). The duration of hospital stay was calculated and classified into those that stayed for <24 hours, 24-72 hours and >72 hours, while the outcome was stated as transferred out, discharged, died, referred, Discharge against medical advice (DAMA) or absconded. The months of May to October were classified as the rainy season, March to April as the hot season, and November to February as the cool, dry season.

Statistical analysis

Data from this study was manually entered into an Excel spreadsheet (Microsoft Excel® 2010) to check for errors and inconsistencies. The cleaned data were exported for analysis into the IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 21) software to produce descriptive statistics. Continuous, normally distributed variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), while continuous skewed variables were expressed as median (interquartile range (IQR)). The categorical variables were presented in frequencies, percentages and charts. Comparison of categorical data was performed using Pearson's Chi-square test, and a p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Missing data were excluded from analyses of the respective variables.

Ethical considerations

Approval was granted from the Health Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, with reference number NHREC/FUHSTHA/11/11/24 before commencement of the study. Information for each patient was kept anonymous and handled confidentially.

Results

Admission details of two thousand nine hundred and seventy-three (2973) children were evaluated retrospectively from the 1st of January 2024 to the 31st of December 2024. Their ages ranged from 1 month to 15 years, with a median (interquartile range) age of 3.0 (6.5) years. Of these, 1802 (60.6%) were aged less than 5 years. There were more male children, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.4:1, and most of the children seen were from Azare and surrounding towns within Bauchi State, as shown in Table 1 below. Most (2545, 85.6%) of the children seen stayed in the unit for 24 to 72 hours, and the unit had the highest admissions during the rainy season.

Morbidity

Severe malaria 871(29.3%), severe acute malnutrition (SAM) 414(13.9%), Sickle Cell Disease(SCD) 347(11.7%), Pneumonia 219(7.4%) and Sepsis 157(5.3%) were. The most common diagnosis at admission. The least cases seen were Tetanus 3(0.1%), Asthma 3(0.1%), Tuberculosis 8(0.3%), Poisoning 17(0.6%) and Diphtheria 22(0.7%) as depicted in Figure 1. Except for Typhoid fever, Tetanus, and Diphtheria, all other infectious diseases were commonly seen in children under the age of 5. (Table 2)

Mortality

Three hundred and ten (310) children out of the 2973 children admitted died during the period of

review, giving a mortality rate of 10.4%. Of the 310 children who died, 214(69.0%) were aged under five years, most of whom were aged between 1 and 5 years, 164(52.9%), while 96(31.0%) were aged 5 years and above. Severe malaria (93, 30.0%), SAM (62, 20.0%), pneumonia (27, 8.7%), acute bacterial meningitis (ABM) (22, 7.1%), and SCD (13, 4.2%) were identified as the common causes of mortality among these children.

The diagnoses with the highest case fatality rates included asthma (33.3%), diphtheria (31.8%), cardiovascular diseases (23.7%), acute bacterial meningitis (21.0%), severe acute malnutrition (15.0%), typhoid fever (15.0%), pertussis (14.8%), and sepsis (14.0%). Figure 2 below depicts the causes of mortality in children admitted into the EPU.

Seasonal Variation

October (15.0%) and November (12.3%) were the months with the highest number of admissions; however, the unit had the highest number of admissions during the rainy season, with 1,293 (43.5%). (Fig. 3) Severe malaria 455(52.2%), SAM 219(52.9%) and SCD 165(47.6%) were mainly encountered in during the rainy season while other infections such as ABM 47(44.8%), Pneumonia 81(37.0%) Measles 68(60.2%) and sepsis 74(47.1%) had the highest admission rates during the warm period. (Fig. 4)

Outcome

A majority (59.3%) of the children admitted were transferred out to other wards for stabilisation or specialist care, while 10(0.3%) absconded from the hospital. (Fig. 5) Children aged 1 to 4.9 years had the highest number across all the outcome variables, followed by children aged 5 to 12 years. A statistically significant relationship was found between the age group and outcome ($p= 0.001$).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of children admitted into the EPU

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Characteristics		
Gender		
Male	1720	57.9
Female	1253	42.1
Age group		
0.1-0.9 years	395	13.3
1-4.9 years	1405	47.2
5-12 years	899	30.2
13-15 years	274	9.2
Residence		
Bauchi	2,888	97.1
Yobe	63	2.1
Jigawa	12	0.4
Gombe	2	0.1

Others 8 0.3

Figure 1: Causes of morbidity in children admitted to the EPU.

Table 2: Common causes of morbidity in children admitted into the EPU based on age group

Diagnosis N(%)	Age-group in years				Total
	0.1-0.9	1-4.9	5-12	13-15	
Severe malaria	49(5.6)	397(45.6)	348(40.0)	77(8.8)	871(100.0)
ABM	28(26.7)	35(33.3)	32(30.5)	10(9.5)	105(100.0)
Pneumonia	74(33.8)	101(46.1)	35(16.0)	9(4.1)	219(100.0)
Typhoid Fever	2(2.3)	5(5.7)	56(64.4)	24(27.6)	87(100.0)
ADDx	34(31.2)	61(56.0)	10(9.2)	4(3.7)	109(100.0)
SAM	72(17.4)	333(80.4)	8(1.9)	1(0.2)	414(100.0)
SCDx	11(3.2)	133(38.3)	152(43.8)	51(14.7)	347(100.0)
Renal Diseases	6(4.2)	31(21.7)	83(58.0)	23(16.1)	143(100.0)
Measles	12(0.6)	80(70.8)	20(17.7)	1(0.9)	113(100.0)
Sepsis	54(34.4)	62(39.5)	28(17.8)	13(8.3)	157(100.0)

N- Number, %- Percentage, ABM- Acute Bacterial Meningitis, ADDx- Acute Diarrhoeal Disease, SCDx- Sickle Cell Disease, Pearson's Chi-square- 969.58, df-69, p= 0.000

Figure 2: Causes of mortality in children admitted into the EPU

Figure 3: Seasonal trends of admissions into the EPU

Figure 4: Seasonal trends of common causes of admission into the EPU

Figure 5: Outcome of children admitted into the EPU

Discussion

The study revealed more males (57.9%) and children under five years of age in the study population. A predominant male admission into the children's emergency ward has also been noted in other studies within and outside Nigeria.^{8,15} A previous study in our facility by Yauba et al, however, revealed an almost equal number of both genders.²¹ The male predominance in this study suggests the cultural and societal preference and preservation of the male child, which may make caregivers more likely to bring them to the hospital despite the general poor health-seeking behaviour. It is also possible that boys may be more susceptible to illnesses, as some have attributed that sex hormones may play a role in immunity.²⁵ A combination of factors, including reduced immunity, poor vaccination uptake, limited access to healthcare facilities, and poverty, may be responsible for the under-five age group susceptibility to infections and other childhood illnesses.

In the current study, severe malaria, severe acute malnutrition, Sickle cell disease, Pneumonia, and Sepsis were the leading causes of admission. Previous studies in this centre, done 10 years earlier and in other States of Nigeria, have shown similar findings.^{13-18,20,21} This study had a lower number of children with acute diarrhoeal disease (3.7%), unlike the other Nigerian studies. It is possible that, at the time this study was carried out, caregivers

had increased knowledge of treating diarrhoea with oral rehydration solution. As such, cases may not have reached the hospital. Also, most children who present to our emergency wards with diarrhoea are malnourished and may be captured as such, giving lower values seen in this study.

Severe malaria, Severe acute malnutrition, pneumonia, acute bacterial meningitis and Sickle cell disease were the leading causes of death among the children studied. Similar findings were observed in studies conducted in some Nigerian healthcare facilities.^{13-17,20}

This study revealed a mortality rate of 10.4%, which is identical to the rate found in the Yauba study (10.6%) in the exact centre 10 years earlier.²¹ This rate is also identical to what was seen in similar studies conducted in Yobe and Sokoto states, the northern parts of Nigeria.^{18,20} Still, it is significantly higher than the rates observed in the southern, Western, and eastern parts of Nigeria and other African countries where similar studies have been conducted.^{7,9-13,15-17} There has been only a slight improvement in the availability of healthcare workers to address the healthcare needs of the studied populace, as well as the availability of required facilities to address emergencies, since the last study, which may explain the similar mortality rates seen. There is a poor health-seeking behaviour and late presentation to hospital seen among the population in this region of Nigeria, with a preference for consulting unorthodox traditional practitioners and the use of over-the-counter medications. This is further complicated by the caregivers' poor socioeconomic status, poor maternal education, and inadequate insurance coverage, which have not improved in the last 10 years. These factors may explain the higher mortality rate seen in this study compared to other parts of the country. The majority of children who died in this study were aged 1 to 5 years (68.7%), which is similar to what was found by Owusu et al and Okworonkwo et al in Ghana and Abia in their studies, respectively.^{10,13} This is unlike the Ezeonwu et al study, which found most of the children who died were aged less than 1 year.¹⁶ The higher morbidity and causes of admission, in addition to their predisposition to infectious diseases and complicated by poor socioeconomic situations, make them likely to die from these diseases. Severe acute malnutrition and acute bacterial meningitis, which contributed significantly to the mortality rate in this age group cohort in this study, were not seen in the Asaba study, which may explain the difference in age distribution of mortality.¹⁶

The months of May to October, which were classified as the rainy season, had the highest number of admissions. A similar trend was also reported by Agbesanwa et al in Ado Ekiti.¹⁷

Severe malaria, SAM and SCD, which all had very high morbidity rates, were mainly seen during this period. Malaria transmission is known to be highest during the rainy season, primarily due to an increase in the number of breeding sites for the female *Anopheles* mosquito.²³ We postulate that food shortages resulting from exhausted supplies just before the rains may be why higher numbers of SAM cases are observed during this period. Other infections, such as acute bacterial meningitis, sepsis, pneumonia and measles, were encountered most often during the warm months.

Approximately two-thirds of the children admitted were transferred to other wards, while the remaining third were discharged. These findings are similar to those observed in Nguru and Sokoto.^{18,20} However, much lower discharge rates (8.9%) and higher transfer rates (76.3%) were observed in a previous study carried out at the same facility a decade ago.²¹ A combination of factors, such as higher patient load and the pressure bed space, a lower threshold for discharge on the part of the healthcare worker, early presentation of some cases and subsequent quicker resolution following treatment, and frequent requests for early discharge by caregivers due to various reasons may explain the higher discharge rates and lower transfer-out rates observed in the current study compared to the survey reported 10 years earlier. There were low rates of referrals, discharges against medical advice and abscondments in this study. The low rate of referrals may be attributed to the increased availability of subspecialists in various medical fields within the hospital compared to 10 years ago. Discharges against medical advice (DAMA) and abscondments are usually associated with prolonged hospital stays. The majority (90.2%) of the children in our study stayed for less than 72 hours, which may explain the low rates observed. The hospital-based, cross-sectional design of this study limits the extrapolation of its findings to the larger population, although similar results have been reported in other parts of the country. Autopsy is not routinely carried out in this region to confirm the cause of death, which may give an accurate picture of the cause of mortality. This study did not examine clinical information, such as the duration of illness and interventions before presentation, which may also influence mortality rates and could be explored in future studies.

Conclusion

Infections remain a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in children in our setting, especially those under the age of five years. This has further been complicated by the high rate of malnutrition in our region. Little to no improvement in care has been observed based on our mortality rates when compared to those of previous years. Ensuring the annual distribution and uptake of early seasonal malaria chemoprophylaxis, reducing food insecurity, and providing continuous education to caregivers on the importance of childhood vaccinations are essential factors to be emphasised by healthcare policymakers. Additionally, improvements in areas such as recruiting skilled personnel, emergency preparedness, providing facilities for emergency care, and offering health insurance to all may help reduce these figures.

References

1. Whithead PR. The lived experience of physicians dealing with patient death. *BMJ Support Palliat Care*. 2014; 4:271-6.
2. Yu H, Wier LM, Elixhauser A. Hospital stays for children, 2009. (2011): Statistical Brief 118. In: *Healthcare Cost and Utilization Project (HCUP)*. Statistical Briefs. Rockville, MD: Agency for healthcare research and quantity (US). [ONLINE] [Cited May 2025] Available at URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK65134>
3. WHO. Disease burden and mortality estimate. WHO (2019) [ONLINE] [Cited May 2025] Available from URL: <https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/mortality-and-global-health-estimates>
4. UN. United Nations. Interagency Group for Child Mortality Estimation. [ONLINE] [Cited April 2025]. Available from URL: <https://childmortality.org/all-cause-mortality/dataestimates>
5. FMOH. Federal Ministry of Health. National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) 2023-2024 Report. [ONLINE] [Cited April 2025] Available from URL: <https://www.ndhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/PR1571PR157.pdf>
6. Lozano R, Naghan M, Foreman K, Lim S, Shibuya K, Aboyans V et al. Global and regional mortality from 235 causes of death for 20 age groups in 1990 and 2010: a systematic analysis for the global burden of

- disease study 2010. *Lancet*. 2012; 380:2095-128
7. Verma S, Singh R. Morbidity profile of children admitted to a regional hospital of Hilly region. *JMSCR*. 2020;8(6)
 8. Mohammed AAA, Imad RM, Hyder MM, Abdullah A, Osama A, Ishag A. Patterns, outcome and predictors of paediatric medical admissions at Gadarif hospital in Eastern Sudan. *Frontiers in Paediatrics*. 2022. [ONLINE] [Cited April 2025] Available from URL: <https://www.frontiersin.org>
 9. Menge I, Esamai F, van Reken D, Anabawani G. Paediatric morbidity and mortality at the Eldoret district hospital Kenya. *East Afr Med J*.1995;72(3):165-9
 10. Owusu SA, Sylverkan J, Asafo-Agyei SB, Ampofo A, Ansong D. Mortality pattern within twenty-four hours of admission to a paediatric emergency room in a teaching hospital in Ghana. *Afr Journal of Curr Med Research*. 2022;5(1) doi:10.31191/afriajcmr.v5;1.104
 11. Lahmini W, Bourrous M. Mortality at the pediatric emergency unit of the Mohammed VI teaching hospital of Marrakech. *BMC Emerg Med*. 2020; 23:20
 12. Onubogu UC, West BA, Azubogu US. The pattern of mortality among children hospitalized in the children emergency ward of a single tertiary hospital in Nigeria. *PEMJ*. 2023;10(1):3-10
 13. Okoronkwo NC, Nduka I, Ogbonna IF. Childhood morbidity and mortality at the children emergency room of a tertiary institution in South East Nigeria: A re-appraisal. *Nigerian Journal of Medicine*. 2019;28(4):375-385
 14. Ejiofor OS, Ofomata JA. Pattern of morbidity and mortality in a children's ward- The Awka experience. *Nigerian Medical Practitioner*. 2010;57(1-2)
 15. Abhulimhen-Iyoha BI, Okolo AA. Morbidity and mortality of childhood illnesses at the emergency paediatric unit of the university of Benin teaching hospital, Benin City. *Niger J Paed*. 2012;39(2):71- 74
 16. Ezeonwu BU, Chima OU, Oguonu T, Ikafuna AN, Nwafor I. Morbidity and mortality pattern of childhood illnesses seen at the children emergency unit of Federal Medical Center, Asaba, Nigeria. *Ann Med Health Sci Res*.2014;(Suppl 3): s239-S244
 17. Agbesanwa TA, Babatola AO, Fatunla OA, Ibrahim A, Aina FO, Ogundare EO et al. Pattern of admissions and outcomes in the children emergency department of a tertiary health institution in Southwestern Nigeria. A four-year review. *Af J Emerg Med*. 2023;18,13(2):45-51
 18. Umar UI, Muhammed IL, Gwarzo GD. Pattern and outcome of admissions at the emergency pediatric unit of Federal Medical Centre, Nguru, Yobe State, Nigeria. *Pyramid Journal of Medicine*. 2018;1(1) doi:
 19. Enyuma COA, Anah MU, Pousson A, Olorunfemi G, Ibisomi L, Abang BE et al. Patterns of paediatric emergency admissions and predictors of prolonged hospital stay at the children emergency room, University of Calabar Teaching Hospital, Calabar, Nigeria. *Afr Health Sci*. 2019;19(2):1910-1923
 20. Isezuo KO, Sani UM, Waziri UM, Garba BI, Adamu A, Jiya Fb et al. Patterns and outcome of emergency paediatric unit admissions in Usmanu Danfodio University Teaching Hospital in Sokoto State, Nigeria: a five-year review. *Pyramid J Med* [ONLINE] 2024 Aug 26 [Cited May 2025] Available from URL: <https://africa.pagepress.net/pjm/article/view/498>
 21. Yauba SM, Ahmed H, Imoudu IA, Yusuf MO, Makarfi HU. Morbidity and mortality of childhood illnesses at the emergency pediatric unit of a tertiary hospital, north-eastern Nigeria. *SMJ*.2015;18(1): p 1-3
 22. Fremantle JM. A history of the region comprising the Katagum division of Kano province. *Journal of the Royal African Society*. 1911; 10:398-421
 23. Malaria prevalence in north-eastern Nigeria: A cross-sectional study. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine*. 2013: 865-8. [ONLINE] [Cited June 2025] Available from URL: <https://www.elsevier.com/locate/apjtm>
 24. WHO. World Health Organization. Targets of sustainable development. [ONLINE] [Cited July 2025] Available from URL: <https://www.who.int>
 25. Piccini P, Montagnani C, De Martino M. Gender disparity in paediatrics: a review of the current literature. *Ital J Pediatr*. 2018;44:1